

THE THEORITICAL FOUNDATIONS, PRACTICAL MECHANISMS, AND LINGUISTIC IMPACT OF SIMULTANEOUS INTERPRETATION IN THE CONTEXT OF GLOBAL COMMUNICATION

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This article intensifies that theoretical foundations, practical mechanisms, and linguistic impact of simultaneous interpretation in the context of global communication. The analyzing of simultaneous interpretation studies is rendered as an activity which closely related to cognitive and communicative activity of people that requires high-levelled professional competence, rapid information processing and of course, cultural awareness. Particular attention is paid to the evolution of SI from its historical emergence in international organizations to its modern transformation through artificial intelligence tools and digital platforms. The article also examines real examples from international communications like conference events, including global health and environmental summits, to demonstrate how interpreters employ adaptation, reformulation, transposition, and contextualization techniques when rendering neologisms from one language into another. Comparative analysis of human interpretation and AI-based translation tools shows limitations of word-for-word translation and emphasizes the significant role of the professional interpreters in ensuring semantic accuracy and communicative effectiveness. That not only transfers meaning between source and target languages but also creates conceptual bridges between different societies. Another main point is that the evolution of Uzbek vocabulary through SI, it totally reflects the dynamic interaction between language development and global discourse.

Interpretation is a general concept, not just in literary studies. Information, it is not a process of interpretation. Interpretation is also revelation based on given oral information. However, they are entirely different things. An interpretation includes transferring information. Interpretation is an art, which combines many arts. Freeman Tilden presented are scientific, historical, or architectural definitions of Interpretation. He mentioned that any art is a degree which can be teachable. The chief aim of interpretation is not instruction, but provocation. Interpretation should aim to present a whole rather than a part, and must address itself to the whole person rather than any phase. Interpretation addressed to children should not be a dilution of the presentation to adults, but should follow a fundamentally different approach. To be at its best it will require a separate program. The development of high leveled contact between nations and the creation of large international organizations led to the birth of a form of interpreting. Language interpreting or interpretation is the intellectual activity of facilitating oral and sign-language communication, either simultaneously or consecutively, between two or more users of different languages. A simultaneous interpreter is may be explained that with looking at the words someone who interprets for someone in another language while the speaker speaks without interruption. It is clear that SI is the opposite of consecutive interpreting, because a consecutive interpreter awaits his turn and does not start

speaking until the speaker allows him the time to do so. Simultaneous interpreting is one of the most common kinds of interpreting, but also the most difficult one. Very few translators who are used to getting the time to really think about their translations, and not even all interpreters can do it well.

Simultaneous interpreting has a number of indisputable advantages over consecutive interpreting and efficiency in conducting international events in which several languages are used the event proceeds at its own pace regardless of the language of the speaker this decreases the time necessary to hold the event and the material resources required and the participants can hear the presentation in the original language without interruption for translation. It is really a very complex process to interpret simultaneously, one that only very few interpreters can handle well. A speaker is speaking constantly, and speaker does not stop or pause even more they continue speaking. Therefore, the interpreter must do the following while the speaker is talking and listen to what the speaker is saying. Context is translated in his mind while rendering the translation in his microphone and this is the most difficult of interpreting.

Simultaneous interpretation stands as a cornerstone profession of global communication, with famous interpreters throughout history leaving a lasting impact on this field. From their important roles in historical events to shaping diplomatic relations, these language experts have played a crucial role in human history so far. As it is explore the evolution of simultaneous interpretation and the rise of new apps and technological advancements in this field, we witness how these innovations have transformed the way languages are bridged in real-life time. In this case, mass media and its materials are widespread and crucial. Because of simultaneously translated words, phrases or contexts will be neologisms and untranslatable words to the target languages. As a result, not only two languages and their lexicology increases but also these kind of words will be the bridges between global languages.

New or newly popularized terms interpreted during global meetings or summits, one of them is held in January 2020 WHO Meeting based on the healthcare problems of humanity in Covid-19. In this case, as an example, the term "*flattening the curve*" is a metaphor for used as a public health strategy to slow down the spread of an epidemic. Moreover, this phrase was not translated literally in many languages of course in Uzbek in 2020. Interpreters often rendered it as something like "*slowing the rise of cases to avoid overwhelming hospitals,*" which helped audiences to understand the concept even without a direct equivalent phrase. In Uzbek language it can be translated if it is eith thr help of the word-for-word translation method *egri chiziqni to'g'irlash* but with the perfect result of the official interpretation activity this phrase was translated like *kasalxonalarga bo'lgan talabni kamaytirish*.

Next example is that "*Our goal is to achieve net-zero emissions by 2050*". This sentence translated simultaneously from English language into Russian with the help of the several AI tools. First one is Google translator. After google translating there is the result: *Наша цель — достичь нулевого выброса к 2050 году*. There are used some techniques like used adaptation and reformulation. Another AI tool is Yandex app. According to the Yandex translation this sentence was translated like *Наша цель — достичь нулевых выбросов к 2050 году*. Between them there is a little bit difference with the suffixes. Especially, Yandex translation widely used word-for-word translation. Transposition and reformulation are still the main techniques which using in the process of SI. Next and the domain device is AI tools. There are several online or even offline types of them like KUDO and Google AI. The result is *Наша цель — достичь*

углеродной нейтральности к 2050 году. Even the modern devices are very helpful and domain in translation process, interpreters in a vital settings like briefings, conference and meetings. There is the translation of real, official interpreter's version, *Мы стремимся к углеродной нейтральности к 2050 году*. As it is seen interpreters are human being with full of experience and qualification. It seems that work of interpreter is clear and also it is easy to understand. There are also plenty of phrases, words and neologisms like: Covid 19, social distance, terrorism and auto-terrorism so on.

The evolution of Uzbek language vocabulary through SI relies to its far-reaching impact not just in language transfer, but in cultural and political integration on a global scale. Simultaneous interpretation is not just about translating words, it is about connecting people across languages and cultures. From the 1940s when the SI began the as a professional field in the worldwide till today, their work has been essential in helping people understand each other and avoid conflict between countries in several situations.

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